

A CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF FOOD

IN TRADITIONAL SOHBET

MEETINGS OF ANATOLIA ¹

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Abstract

This study investigates the significance of food within the framework of Traditional Sohbet Meetings, an essential component of Anatolia's Intangible Cultural Heritage. Through a comprehensive content analysis of academic sources, including articles, papers, and theses, this study examines the role of food in ten gatherings from various regions of Anatolia. The findings indicate that these meetings, predominantly held during the winter months, serve purposes such as socialization, entertainment and education. Meal preparation varied, with either the host or all participants contributing to the culinary process. The timing of meal presentation also differed, occurring either before or after the conversation. Cuisine predominantly reflects local traditions, although lighter appetizers are often served because of the late schedule of certain gatherings. Beverages, particularly Turkish coffee and tea, played a crucial role in the meetings. The study also uncovered symbolic meanings associated with food, such as mirran representing unity and solidarity, seating arrangements reflecting hierarchical structures, and the educational dimension of communal learning. Furthermore, a leader's initiation of a meal underscores its status aspect. This study concludes that food transcends its physiological necessity, emerging as a multifaceted sociocultural phenomenon with diverse interpretations within the context of Traditional Sohbet Meetings.

Key Words: Traditional Sohbet Meetings, Food, Gastronomy

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ANADOLU'NUN GELENEKSEL SOHBET TOPLANTILARINDA YEMEKLERİN KÜLTÜREL ANALİZİ

Öz

Bu çalışma, Anadolu'nun somut olmayan kültürel mirasının önemli bir bileşeni olan Geleneksel Sohbet Toplantıları çerçevesinde yemeğin önemini araştırmaktadır. Makaleler, bildiriler ve tezler de dahil olmak üzere akademik kaynakların kapsamlı bir içerik analizi yoluyla, bu çalışma Anadolu'nun çeşitli bölgelerinden yemeğin rolünü incelemektedir. Bulgular, ağırlıklı olarak kış aylarında düzenlenen bu toplantıların sosyalleşme, eğlence ve eğitim gibi amaçlara hizmet ettiğini göstermektedir. Yemek hazırlama, ev sahibi veya tüm katılımcıların mutfak sürecine katkıda bulunmasıyla çeşitlilik göstermektedir. Yemek sunumunun zamanlaması da sohbetten önce veya sonra gerçekleşerek farklılık göstermektedir. Mutfak, ağırlıklı olarak yerel gelenekleri yansıtsa da bazı toplantıların geç saatleri nedeniyle genellikle daha hafif mezeler servis edilmektedir. İçecekler, özellikle Türk kahvesi ve çayı, toplantılarda önemli bir rol oynamaktadır. Çalışma ayrıca, birlik ve beraberliği temsil eden Mirra'nın, hiyerarşik yapıları yansıtan oturma düzenlemeleri ve toplumsal öğrenmenin eğitim boyutu gibi yiyeceklerle ilişkili sembolik anlamları da ortaya çıkarmıştır. Dahası, bir liderin bir yemeği başlatması, onun statü yönünü vurguladığı da görülmüştür. Bu çalışma, Geleneksel Sohbet Toplantıları bağlamında, gıdanın fizyolojik gerekliliğinin ötesinde, çok yönlü, farklı yorumlara sahip sosyokültürel bir olgu olarak ortaya çıktığı sonucuna varmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Geleneksel Sohbet Toplantıları, Yemek, Gastronomi

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INTRODUCTION

Anatolia is geographically positioned between the Black Sea to the north, the territories of Upper Mesopotamia and the Levant to the south, the Taurus mountain range spanning the south and southeast, the eastern region where the Caucasus, Zagros, and Elbrus mountain ranges intersect (Gür, 2017), and the Aegean Sea to the west. Owing to its location, this landmass has been a natural pedestrian passageway for all living things on their journeys between continents in the prehistoric and posthistoric periods. Due to this feature, the Anatolian land has hosted the establishment of important civilizations that have resided, fought, conquered, and established states for thousands of years with migrations, and in this respect, it is a geography where traces of Western and Eastern cultural heritage are seen together. The Aegean migrations, which started with the famine that occurred after a severe drought in the late 13th and early 12th centuries BC, are considered to be the most basic source and beginning of this cultural diversity, followed by Persian raids, Alexander the Great's Asian Campaign, Roman Dominion, Hun raids, Turkish migration, and Crusades reshaped this geography, known as Asia Minor,

politically, socially, and ethnically, and caused the formation of mixed nations (Çetin, 2017). The etymological investigation of the term "Anatolia" reveals its roots in the ancient Greek word "ανατέλλω." This term, "anatéllō ανατέλλω," frequently appears in lexical sources and is derived from the ancient Greek verb "τέλλω, τολ- τέλλω, τολ," which translates to "to get up, lift," combined with the prefix "ana." The word signifies "sunrise" (TürkçeBilgi, 2019). It is conceivable that "Anatolia" functioned as a slogan during the Aegean migrations, and for centuries, it has been used to denote a region characterized by its diverse ethnic composition. According to Harrington (2005), cultural phenomena such as history, ethnic diversity, traditions, and religious values are significant factors that enrich culinary culture. Anatolia has historically been a site of interaction among various ethnic groups since ancient times, attributable to the aforementioned environmental and cultural factors. Such intense interactions have culminated in a rich culinary culture characterized not only by distinctive dishes but also by diverse consumption patterns. In essence, food serves not only as a physiological necessity, but also as a vehicle for social integration and solidarity. Social phenomena, including friendly conversations, gatherings, travel, hosting guests, offerings, festivals, and religious ceremonies, have facilitated the establishment of a communicative network within society, parallel to the development of food culture (Sağır, 2012).

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Traditional Sohbet Meetings, a fundamental component of social interactions involving food, are known by various names across different regions of Anatolia. These gatherings are typically characterized by dialogue and musical performances intended to provide entertainment and enjoyment, with food and beverages serving as central elements. Consequently, these traditional gatherings have been recognized on UNESCO's Intangible Cultural Heritage list. In this context, food plays a significant role (Sağır, 2012). This study examined the presence of food remnants in traditional Anatolian Sohbet Meetings and interpreted the symbolic significance of food within these cultural interactions.

1. Purpose and Scope

Food transcends basic physiological functions and encompasses multiple sociocultural, economic, and psychological dimensions. A comprehensive exploration of this subject

can provide deeper insight into the role of food culture in human society. This study aimed to investigate the multifaceted nature of food in the context of Traditional Sohbet Meetings. This research focuses on the significance of food in "Traditional Sohbet Meetings," which are recognized by various names across different regions of Anatolia. These gatherings are locally known as "Leyli Night," "Yaren Night," "Gezek Nights," "Kursubashi Entertainment," "Barana Nights," "Oturma Night," "Sira Night," "Ateş Gezmesi," "Helebish Gezmesi," and "Velime Nights," and the scope of the study is delineated by these regional designations.

2. Method

This study utilized a qualitative methodology, focusing on data derived from studies of Traditional Sohbet Meetings in Anatolia. The literature contains numerous document-based investigations into regional culinary traditions (Nebioğlu, 2017). This study employed a similar methodology to explore the presence of food within Sohbet meetings in Anatolia, as informed by the findings of prior studies. The results yielded significant insights into the food culture inherent in these gatherings. This study strictly adhered to the procedural guidelines set forth by Creswell (2013) for data collection, analysis, and presentation of the results. Throughout the study, methodological rigor and adherence to scientific and ethical standards were consistently maintained.

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In accordance with the research objectives, a comprehensive review of the local literature was conducted to identify studies exploring traditional sohbet meetings in Anatolia. Consequently, these gatherings were analyzed with respect to their regional context, schedule, purpose, food served, and symbolic significance of the food. Two researchers independently conducted the content analysis. Subsequently, the researchers compared their findings and categorized them into relevant themes. In addition, a descriptive study was conducted by obtaining data from secondary sources. In this context, an ethics committee decision was not required to obtain the data needed for the research.

3. Findings

This study investigated the role of food-related aspects in Anatolian conversational assemblies by organizing the findings into four categories. The categories are as follows:
LSWS

1. Locations, where the meetings are convened and the regional appellations of the conversational gatherings,
2. Schedule of Traditional Sohbet Meetings
3. Way, what the dish is prepared
4. Symbolic meanings of what the dishes served

3.1. Locations Where The Meetings Are Convened and The Regional Appellations of The Conversational Gatherings

An analysis of the documents indicated that Traditional Sohbet Meetings conducted across various regions of Anatolia are identified by distinct names. For example:

"Leyli Night" in Mardin (Uygur, 2014),

"Yaren Night" in Afyon, Çankırı, Manisa, Kütahya, Kastamonu (KTB, 2019),

"Gezek Nights" in Isparta, Burdur, Sandıklı (Özeski, 2011),

"Kürsübaşı Entertainments" in Elâzığ (Taşbilek, 2012),

"Oturma Night" in Van (Kali, 2007),

"Sıra Night" in Şanlıurfa (Akbıyık, 2006),

"Ateş Gezmeleri" in Bolu (Akay, 2011),

"Helebish Night" in Kırşehir (Merdin, 2016),

"Velime Night" in Diyarbakır (Atlı, 2016).

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3.2. Schedule of Traditional Sohbet Meetings

It is widely acknowledged that these gatherings are predominantly held during winter. These events are defined as entertainment-focused occasions that occur in winter, primarily because of the cold climate and prolonged evenings characteristic of this season (Taşbilek, 2012). In the context of Anatolia's severe winter conditions, these gatherings, which include shared meals, play a crucial role in fostering communication and sustaining neighborly relations, thereby ensuring that participants remain informed about one another (Kali, 2007). In the Southeastern Anatolia region, particularly during the winter

months when agricultural activities are less demanding, groups of acquaintances convene weekly, taking turns to host gatherings at a member's residence or a communal venue. These gatherings, referred to as "Sıra night," are characterized by their commencement in the evening and continuing until the early morning hours (Akbiyık, 2006; Aslan, 2014; Atlı, 2016).

3.3. Way, What The Dish is Prepared

Research on the culinary practices observed during Anatolian conversational gatherings indicates that the methods of meal preparation differ between meetings. In certain instances, the host assumed full responsibility for preparing the food, whereas in others, a collaborative approach was employed. During events such as Helebish Nights, Velime Nights, and Sitting Nights, a division of labor is evident among attendees, with each participant contributing home-cooked food items. This collective spirit fosters the creation of abundant and diverse dining experiences, exemplifying the principles of communal sharing (Göktürk, 2006).

The scheduling of food presentations at traditional Sohbet gatherings is typically divided into two segments: prior to the commencement of the conversation (e.g., Leyli Night, Oturma Night, Ateş Night, and Velime Night) and, in certain instances, subsequent to the conversation (e.g., Gezek night and Sıra Night). For instance, during Oturma Night (Sitting Night) in the Van region, the sequence begins with the serving of food after the arrival of guests, followed by conversations and music. This arrangement illustrates that each gathering was molded by its unique cultural framework and traditions, thereby reflecting Anatolia's rich cultural diversity.

Anatolian Sohbet meetings play a pivotal role in showcasing local culinary traditions. This initiative is vital for preserving ancient recipes and promoting regional gastronomic legacies. During these gatherings, particularly on Leyli nights, a diverse array of main dishes is presented, including Çiğköfte, İçli Köfte, Bumbar, İhbeyz, Lahme, Senbusek, İkbebet, and Ciğer Sote. Cultural richness is further highlighted by dishes such as Allüciye, Döboy, Firkiye Hamis, İncasiyye, Kibe, Kaliyye, Meftune, Lamb Injik with Molasses, Selcemiye, and Irok. The assortment of desserts and snacks, featuring walnut

sausage, grapes, pestil, bittim, walnuts, almonds, molasses halva, fruits, and nuts, illustrates the profound and enduring heritage of local cuisine (Uygun, 2014).

The culinary diversity of Kırşehir's local cuisine is prominently highlighted during Helebiş Night. The meal typically begins with starters, such as Çökelek cheese and Yufka bread. Appetizers often include purple pürçüklü roast, quince borani, and water pastries. The main courses are distinguished by dishes such as Sızgıt, Mantı, Köğtür (köftür) and Çirleme. The primary choices for desserts are quince desserts, cat batmaz, and hoşmerim (Merdin, 2016; Güner, 2017).

Gezek night offers a remarkable showcase of traditional Turkish culinary arts. The soup selection is notably diverse, featuring options such as okra, toyga, creamy rice, and talash soups. Appetizers often include börek, stuffed pencils, and stuffed pepper. The main courses included dishes such as okra with sour chorizo, lamb stew and Tiftik kebab. The meal concludes with desserts such as rice pudding, raisins, and baklava, which are notable for their 52 layers of clotted cream (Özeski, 2011).

The culinary offerings during the Ateş Gezmeleri typically commence with "Cranberry Tarhana and Uhut Soup" as appetizers. This was followed by "Keşkek," which served as the main dish. The meal is complemented by "Keş" as a side accompaniment, and it concludes with "Saray Halva" for dessert (Mudurnu Municipality, 2019).

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Velime Night in Diyarbakır is characterized by the preparation and serving of raw meatballs, followed by the selection of main dishes, including meftune, dizme (celebrated for its pure flavor), duvaklı pilaf, and beli tied. The meal concludes with desserts, such as dilberdudağı, künefe (cheese kadayif), and lebzuniye, which are renowned for their melting sensations on the lips (Doru, 2013).

In the context of gatherings in Van, the culinary experience is initiated with the serving of freshly baked tandoori bread and taptapa, accompanied by a selection of herbed cheese infused with thyme, wild garlic, mendo, çaşur, and mountain mint. The assortment of appetizers includes traditional dishes such as Çirişli, Murtuga, Cılbır, İlitme, a quince-based dish, Keledoş, pearl mullet cooked in a tandoor, Şille, Mıhla, Kurdish meatballs, helise (Keşkek), and fried plums as a sweet conclusion. Following a meal, tea, particularly brewed in a samovar, is provided throughout the evening, fostering an environment

conducive to engaging in conversation and musical entertainment (Tan and Turhan, 2001).

The aforementioned examples demonstrate that meals that reflect local culinary heritage are predominantly featured at these gatherings. Additionally, lighter, appetizer-type foods are occasionally consumed. For instance, Kürsübaşı gatherings in Elâzığ are noted for their infrequent food provision (Atlı, 2016). During these events, it is customary to offer çiğköfte and patıl bread along with orcik and pestil (Çetintaş, 2019).

Similar to Elâzığ Kürsübaşı entertainment, Urfa queue nights do not feature many substantial meals either. Çiğköfte plays a central role in these celebrations. Depending on the season, accompaniments such as lettuce, cucumber, mint, pırpırım (purslane), and herbs such as sorrel, siyarpızı, and cress are served alongside raw köfte. Ayran is also available to those who prefer it along with their çiğköfte. Additionally, cacık (tzatziki), koruk salad, shepherd's salad, and olive orchards are served with raw meatballs. Local desserts, including kadayif, katmer, şıllık (lavash bread soaked in sugar water), dash bread, Küncülü Akıt, Palıza, Baklava, and Shire, are served after the Çiğköfte (Can, 2010).

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Certain beverages consumed during these cultural gatherings are particularly significant, with coffee being the most prominent. Coffee plays a vital role in Turkish culture and is a fundamental element of traditional conversations. For example, during the Gezeks of Gezek, Turkish coffee is served before meals are served. Conversely, during Urfa queue nights, mirra, a robust variant of coffee, is offered to guests at both the beginning and end of the event, signifying the welcoming and farewell stages. The process of preparing, presenting, and consuming coffee follows traditional practices, including thorough boiling in a copper pitcher. The coffee is then served in small handleless cups to the participants in the queue. Importantly, only one cup is shared among attendees during the coffee presentations (Varlı and Çılgın, 2019).

Tea is another beverage frequently consumed during traditional gatherings. It plays a crucial role and is consumed throughout the night during specific cultural events such as the Sitting Nights (Van; a province of Türkiye).

Pleasant tea is another beverage that garners attention during these events. The significance of welcoming people to these gatherings is notably heightened. In Bolu, these

events are referred to as Hoşaf crawls. During these gatherings, the most renowned local pleasantries, such as plums and pear pleasantries, are offered to guests during dinners and throughout the evening's discussions (Mudurnu Municipality, 2019).

3.4. Symbolic Meanings of What The Dishes Served

The ingredients used to create each dish, along with the culinary techniques and presentation methods, illuminate the profound historical and cultural heritage of Turkish cuisine. These dishes not only gratify the palate but also convey a cultural narrative that reflects the history, traditions, and lifestyle of a society. With these attributes, Turkish cuisine transcends mere gustatory pleasure and acts as a conduit for historical and social connection. Fundamentally, the role of food in social gatherings extends beyond satisfying basic physiological needs and embodying significant symbolic meanings. For instance, the custom of serving mirran in a single cup to all participants during Şanlıurfa-specific Sira nights is a pivotal ritual that signifies communal unity and solidarity among participants. This tradition exemplifies the strengthening of interpersonal bonds and sharing of collective values. Varlı and Çılgın (2019) highlight that such symbolic practices are crucial in reinforcing social cohesion and collective identity. Furthermore, the preparation of tables by young men at these gatherings (Okay, 2011; Varlı and Çılgın, 2019) and the seating of guests according to their social status and musical knowledge indicate an established hierarchy at these meals. Additionally, the commencement of the meal by the individual known as the head agha, who takes the first spoonful, underscores the status symbol of the meal (KTB, 2019).

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The Eyvan tradition, centered in and around Diyarbakır, involves community gatherings following meals, where participants engage in discussions about the city's cultural, social, and economic matters. During these sessions, families requiring assistance were identified, and their needs were assessed meticulously. Solutions were then formulated to effectively address the needs of students. The identified needs are subsequently communicated to local authorities to ensure the organization of necessary aid. This tradition not only strengthens interpersonal relationships but also plays a crucial role in addressing social issues (Küçükuncular, 2019; Laçın, 2020; Laçın, 2023).

Kürsübaşı conversations, traditionally held in and around Elâzığ, are gatherings of cultural significance to the local community. These events create a space where

individuals assemble around a burning barbecue to exchange their joys and sorrows, accompanied by refreshments such as tea and nuts. While these conversations cultivate a lively atmosphere with folk songs and entertainment, they also function as platforms for expressing grief and sorrow through poignant stories and lamentations. The seating arrangement at these gatherings is traditionally hierarchical, with the elderly and wise-seated before the younger and less experienced ones. Guests are given special consideration and typically seated at the head of the table. Discussions were led by elder sages, who were the most experienced and respected community members. Initially, the community's general issues were addressed, grievances were resolved, and solutions were sought for the problems of those in need. Additionally, plaintiffs and defendants are heard, and a fair decision is made after evaluating the perspectives of the parties involved. These assemblies play a crucial role in fostering social solidarity and justice (Aydın and Ünüvar, 2020). In this context, Kürsübaşı has evolved into a tradition of entertainment and a symbol of social solidarity and emotional connections.

According to Can (2010), Anatolian Sohbet gatherings serve purposes beyond mere nourishment, encompassing educational and instructive elements that prepare individuals for active engagement in community life and impart societal etiquette. The culinary offerings and traditional practices observed during these events have been shaped and enriched by the historical influence of numerous civilizations. By amalgamating distinctive flavors from various geographical regions, Anatolian cuisine has established a cultural heritage that has garnered attention both nationally and internationally.

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CONCLUSION

This study examines the role of food in Traditional Sohbet Meetings, a significant aspect of Anatolia's intangible cultural heritage. This study draws on academic sources, including articles, papers, and theses, to inform its analysis. Through a comprehensive document review, this study incorporated ten Traditional Sohbet Meetings from various regions of Anatolia to explore the role of food in these gatherings. Table 1 presents the findings related to the presence and significance of food during these meetings.

Tablo 1. Findings on the Phenomenon of Food in Anatolia's Traditional Sohbet Meetings

Main Themes	Brief Explanations on Themes
Times for Organizing the Conversation	In winter
Reasons for Organizing Nights	Socialization, entertainment and education
Preparation of Meals	Responsibility of landlords
	By hand, with the support of the participants
Food Presentation Time	Before the Sohbet
	After the Sohbet
Characteristics of the Dishes	Reflecting the local cuisine
	Offering non-heavy snacks at some meals
Drinks Consumed at Meetings	The emergence of coffee as an important element in some gatherings (e.g. Urfa Night- Murra, Gezek Nights, Ateş Gezmeleri- Turkish coffee)
	Consuming tea overnight
	Consumption of refreshments (e.g. Ateş Gezmeleri)
Symbolic Aspects of Food	Symbolizing unity and solidarity (consumption of murra with a single cup)
	Hierarchical structure at the table (the table is prepared by young people and people's place at the table is determined by their social position)
	The educational aspect (these meals are a lesson that teaches young people about community life)
	Being a status symbol (not starting the meal without the most respected person who is seen as the leader)

The findings indicate that these Sohbet meetings are primarily scheduled during the winter months to serve purposes such as socialization, entertainment, and education. In some instances, the host was solely responsible for meal preparation, whereas in other cases, all participants participated in the culinary process.

The schedule of the meal presentation varies, occurring either prior to or following the conversation. Cuisines predominantly mirror local traditions; however, due to the late schedule of certain gatherings, lighter appetizers are frequently offered. Beverages play a crucial role in these meetings, with Turkish coffee and tea being the most commonly consumed beverages. Occasionally, the attendees enjoyed Hoshaf. Food embodies several

symbolic meanings. Mirran is emblematic of unity and solidarity, while the seating arrangement and involvement of younger individuals in table preparation reflect a hierarchical structure. The educational dimension is underscored by communal learning experiences associated with meals. Furthermore, the initiation of a meal depends on the leader, which underscores its status.

As shown in Table 1, food transcends its role as a mere physiological necessity for satiating hunger and emerges as a crucial sociocultural phenomenon with various interpretations. This study attempts to uncover the multifaceted nature of food by leveraging insights from the existing academic literature. However, this study had some limitations. The foremost limitation was the exclusive reliance on document analysis for data collection. Additionally, the research was limited to an examination of only ten gatherings. Future investigations could expand their scope by including more traditional conversations. Moreover, subsequent research could be enhanced by incorporating interviews with organizers of these gatherings.

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